

Design and Analysis of Fiber-reinforced Composite Hydrogen Storage Vessels for Transportation Vehicles Type IV and V

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Introduction

- Hydrogen storage vessels are categorized into types I through V.
- Among these, Type IV composite-structured vessels achieve high-efficiency lightweight characteristics by utilizing polymer liners instead of traditional metal liners. Moreover, Type V hydrogen vessels integrate polymer liners into composite structures to achieve maximum efficiency.
- In the case of hydrogen storage vessels for vehicles, the structure is constrained, necessitating structural optimization to maximize spatial efficiency. Type 4 storage vessels are primarily composed of a polymer liner for hydrogen storage and a composite structure that withstands load and pressure. Therefore, the characteristics of the liner and the design of the pressure vessel structure are critical.
- This study thus focuses on the design and simulation of a multi-cylinder, curved hydrogen storage vessel to transportation applications. Additionally, the Polyamide 12(PA12), intended as the liner material, was reinforced by the addition of graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) to examine and enhance its properties. Finally, the properties of the hydrogen storage vessel were verified through pressure test.

Experimental

1. Materials

- Polyamide 12(PA12, Grilamid L 25A NZ, Griltech, Switzerland)
- Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs, Sigma Aldrich (USA))
- T-700 12K UD prepreg(Toray, Japan)

2. Manufacturing

- Resin
 - 3 Kg master batch
 - Dried over 30 mins with vacuum dry oven
 - Hot press – 15 bar, 180 °C
- Composites
 - Single braided winding

Samples	GNPs wt.%
Pristine	0.0
G0.3	0.3
G0.6	0.6
G0.9	0.9

PA12 Resin component with GNPs

3. Characterization

- Thermal conductivity
- DSC
- X-ray CT
- Drop weight

4. Numerical analysis

- ABAQUS/Implicit
- Shell structure with inner pressure

Results & Discussion

PA12 resin

Thermal conductivity(left) and DSC curves(right) of PA12 resin according to GNPs content

- A thermal conductivity analysis was conducted to examine the thermal properties of liners with indicating an increase according to GNPs content. However, a decrease was observed at G0.9. The trend suggests that better dispersion of GNPs, which act as thermal conductors, and it can be optimized.
- Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analysis was conducted to measure changes in melting point and enthalpy. The melting points for Pristine, G0.3, G0.6, and G0.9 were 176.54°C, 175.57°C, 174.85°C, and 175.17°C respectively, with no significant changes. However, the enthalpy increased by 3.1% at G0.3 and 8.5% at G0.6, while it decreased by 6.8% at G0.9 compared to G0.6.

Representative Drop weight impact result of PA12 resin according to GNPs content

- The peak forces measured for Pristine, G0.3, G0.6, and G0.9 were 2030, 4961, 5007, and 4633 N, respectively. The peak energies were 12.15, 53.18, 54.08, and 49.25J, and the total energies were 41.76, 119.08, 121.24, and 117.38 J, respectively.
- This increase is attributed to the uniform distribution of GNPs within the PA12 panel, which enhances impact absorption. However, a decreasing trend was observed at G0.9, likely due to the agglomeration of GNPs, which results in uneven dispersion and reduced impact absorption.

CFRP pressure vessel

Representative X-ray CT image of CFRP composite vessel

Hydrogen storage vessel failure behavior. Uniform thickness model (top) and Uniform material model (bottom)

Efficiency of hydrogen storage. Typical single cylinder model (left) and multi-cylinder model (right)

- CFRP composite samples were fabricated for hydrogen storage vessels and analyzed through numerical simulations. Initially, the manufacturing process was verified using micro-CT to examine the internal structure. Although voids were present, the samples were manufactured stably without issues regarding fiber orientations, and no significant problems were found at the resin interfaces.
- Numerical analysis was conducted to optimize the curved structure. The analysis simulated a multi-cylinder curved structure to assess potential failure at bends or cross-sectional changes upon fabrication. The results shows that a uniform material model naturally thickens in areas of decreasing diameter, confirming the structural integrity of the design.
- Finally, the multi-cylinder curved structure was shown to be more efficient compared to the single-cylinder structure. The storage efficiency of the multi-cylinder model was found to be 7.4% higher than that of a typical single-cylinder model. In actual vehicle storage compartments, which typically have a rectangular structure, and the efficient interconnection of the multi-cylinder model resulted in an efficiency improvement of over 15%.

Conclusion and further works

- In this study, we explored polymer resins suitable for use as liner materials for the production of high-efficiency, lightweight hydrogen storage vessels for vehicles.
- A multi-cylinder, curved Type IV hydrogen storage vessel utilizing these resins. The PA12 resin, enhanced with graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs), exhibited excellent mechanical properties and hydrogen barrier performance, facilitating efficient hydrogen storage vessel design.
- Moreover, the proposed curved hydrogen storage vessel achieves over 7% greater area efficiency and more than 15% greater space efficiency compared to conventional single-cylinder structures. The feasibility of this design was examined through numerical analysis and experimental.
- This research was supported by the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Energy (Project Number 20011899), and further studies on the hydrogen barrier properties of the resin, as well as pressure and charging tests of the actual multi-cylinder hydrogen storage vessel, are currently underway.